

Schedule-I
LETTER OF AUTHORIZATION

AFFIDAVIT/AUTHORIZATION FOR LETTER OF ADMINISTRATION/SUCCESSION CERTIFICATE

1. I **Muhammad Arshad** Son of **Sheikh Abdul Aziz** bearing CNIC/NICOP No. **35102-7977836-3** do hereby state on oath that legal heirs mentioned below have authorized undersigned to act on their behalf for the purpose of filling the application for the grant of succession certificate/Letter of Administration in respect of moveable/immovable properties (mentioned below) of the deceased **Mr. Sheikh Muhammad Anwar abid** Son of **Sheikh Abdul Aziz** bearing CNIC/NICOP No. 35102-9418934-7

2. The details of the legal heirs and moveable/immovable properties are given below: -

(a) Details of Moveable /Immovable Properties		
Sr.	Assets type	Assets description
1	immovable	Registry 15 Marla plot , Tariq colony Kasur , intiqal no, khata no 198/199, khatoni no 1269, khasra no 6038, part of 8k-15m , hawala intiqal warasat no 3319 manzoor shuda 30-1-79, hawala intiqal warasat no 4363 manzoor shuda 1-12-80
2	Immovable	Chamber no 72 , district courts Kasur
3	Moveable	HBL-Kasur dingarh branch , Ac no = PK04 HABB 0010660007006701,Title=Sh M anwar abid , balance=238,119
4	Moveable	BRANCH 1512-KASUR-I-BEHBOOD SAVING CERTIFICATES (Registration no 151200040012496 certificate no CA687995 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040012634 certificate no CB248313 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040012798 certificate no DE976262 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040012823 certificate no CB248363 RS 50,000), (Registration no certificate no CB248364 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040012931 certificate no DE976441 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040012997 certificate no DE976530 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040013118 certificate no DE976704 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040013269 certificate no DE976919 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040013302 certificate no DE976971 RS 100,000) (Registration no 151200040013393 certificate no CB248766 RS 50,000 , certificate no 248767 RS 50,000). (Registration no 151200040013545 certificate no DF457643 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015151 certificate no DE391353 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015191 certificate no DE391412 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015192 certificate no DE391413 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015209 certificate no DE391444 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015210 certificate no DE391445 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040015973 certificate no DF620127 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040016166 certificate no DF620444 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040016204 certificate no DF620489 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040016375 certificate no DF620756 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040017462 certificate no DG125459 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040017463 certificate no DG125460 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040017539 certificate no CB283807 RS 50,000, CB283808 RS 50,000) (Registration no 151200040017540 certificate no CB283809 RS 50,000), (Registration no certificate no CB283810 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040017584 certificate no DG358034 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040017599 certificate no DG358055 RS 100,000), (Registration no 151200040018078 certificate no CB553564 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040018081 certificate no CB553565 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040019365 certificate no CB548767 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040019470 certificate no CB548794 RS 50,000), (Registration no 151200040021516 certificate no's DH893246 RS 100,000, DH893247 RS 100,000, DH893248 RS 100,000, DH893249 RS 100,000) GRAND TOTAL : 3,100,000 PKR (THREE MILLION ONE HUNDRED THOUSAND ONLY) PROFIT AMOUNT 3,937 PKR (THREE THOUSAND NINE HUNDRED THIRTY SEVEN ONLY)

I ACKNOWLEDGE THAT THE ESTIMATED VALUE OF AFOREMENTIONED MOVEABLE/IMMOVABLE ASSETS IS APPROXIMATELY

Rs _____ (MORE THAN RS 100,000)

(B) LEGAL HEIR'S DETAILS (INCLUDE ALL LEGAL HEIRS)											
SR	NAME	CNIC	GENDER	RELATION WITH APPLICANT	RELATION WITH DECEASED	RELIGION	SECT	CELL NO	EMAIL	SHARE OF LEGAL HEIR OF ALL ASSETS	THUMB/ SIGN
1	Muhammad Arshad	35102-7977836-3	M		BROTHER	ISLAM		0303-9909095		2/6	
2	KHURSHED BEGUM	35102-6652454-0	F	SISTER	SISTER	ISLAM		0322-4991701		1/6	
3	KHALIDA PARVEEN	35202-9978506	F	SISTER	SISTER	ISLAM		0322-4891275		1/6	
4	ABIDA KAUSAR	35012-6234618-8	F	SISTERS	SISTER	ISLAM		0321-8878111		1/6	
5	USMA NAZ AJMAL	35202-5521338-4	F	SISTER	SISTER	ISLAM		0344-4786444		1/6	

3. I MUHAMMAD ARSHAD THE ABOVE NAMED APPLICANT DO HEREBY STATE ON OATH AND DECLARE THAT LIST OF LEGAL HEIR(S) AND DETAILS OF ASSETS PROVIDED BY ME ARE TRUE AND CORRECT TO BEST OF MY KNOWLEDGE

DATED THIS _____ DAY OF _____ AT _____

SIGN/THUMB IMPRESSION OF APPLICANT

ATTESTED BY OATH COMMISSIONER